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CSR AS A CATALYST FOR MSME PERFORMANCE: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL BEHAVIOR, SOCIAL CAPITAL, AND EMPOWERMENT IN PT BIO FARMA'S PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to investigate the impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR), with the aim of exploring how CSR programs, social capital, and empowerment influence small business behavior and performance. The methodology adopted for this research comprises a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative. Data collection was carried out through a descriptive, explanatory survey to explore relationships between variables, while the qualitative aspect involves Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) to deepen understanding and validate finding]. The results obtained revealed the critical role of CSR partnerships, social capital, and empowerment in enhancing entrepreneurial behavior and small business performance. In the discussion section, these results are contextualized considering the theoretical framework, highlighting the implications and relationships identified. Possible discrepancies and limitations of the study are also considered in this section. The practical and theoretical implications of this research are discussed, providing insights into how the results can be applied or influence practices in the field of CSR. These implications could encompass policymakers and CSR practitioners, suggesting that CSR programs should focus on building social capital, empowering small businesses, and fostering entrepreneurial behavior to achieve sustainable business growth. This study contributes to the literature by practical contributions. The relevance and value of this research are evidenced by the importance of unrestricted funding, trust-based relationships, and self-reliance initiatives in fostering entrepreneurial behavior and improving small business performance.

KEYWORDS: Corporate Social Responsibility, Entrepreneurial Behavior, Social Capital, Empowerment, Small And Medium Enterprises, Indonesia.

1. INTRODUCTION

The economy of Southeast Asia heavily relies on the support of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), which serve as the backbone of the region's economic development. MSMEs drive domestic demand, create employment opportunities, and foster domestic and international innovation and competition. According to data from Developing Member Countries (DMCs), MSMEs in Southeast Asia contribute an average of 97.2% of all business

establishments, 69.4% of the total workforce, and 41.1% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) during the period 2010–2019 (Asian Development Bank, 2021). In Indonesia, MSMEs play a pivotal role, with 64.2 million units contributing 61.07% to the national GDP in 2021 (Ministry of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), 2021). Despite their significant contributions, MSME small businesses face persistent challenges such as low productivity, limited access to technology, and intense competition in the digital era.

Figure 1: Growth Of Smes In Indonesia 2018-2019 (Ministry Of Cooperatives And Smes, 2021).

In West Java, the growth of MSMEs has shown a consistent upward trend, with small businesses increasing annually from 2016 to 2020 (Ministry of

Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), 2021).

Figure 2: Growth Of Smes In West Java 2016-2020 (Department Of Cooperatives And Smes Of West Java, 2021).

However, this growth has not been accompanied by a proportional improvement in business performance. Many small businesses struggle with

fluctuating sales, limited financing access, and difficulties adapting to digital transformation. The COVID-19 pandemic further exacerbated these

challenges, with 56% of MSMEs reporting a decline in sales, 22% facing challenges in obtaining financing, and 15% experiencing distribution issues (Ministry of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), 2021). These obstacles highlight the need for targeted interventions to enhance the performance and sustainability of small businesses.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has emerged as a strategic tool for empowering MSMEs through partnership programs and community development initiatives. PT Bio Farma, a state-owned enterprise in the health sector, has implemented CSR programs aimed at empowering small businesses in West Java. These programs include soft loans, capacity-building training, and mentoring to improve small businesses' managerial and operational capabilities. PT Bio Farma's CSR initiatives align with sustainable development principles, focusing on economic, social, and environmental impacts. For instance, in 2016, PT Bio Farma disbursed IDR 5.7 billion to 240 small business partners, focusing on sectors such as trade, agriculture, and crafts (Bio Farma, 2016).

Despite the growing body of literature on CSR and business performance, there is limited research on how CSR initiatives influence small business behavior, social capital, and empowerment in Indonesia. Existing studies have primarily focused on the direct impact of CSR on business performance, often overlooking the mediating roles of entrepreneurial behavior, social networks, and community empowerment. This study aims to address this gap by examining the impact of PT Bio Farma's CSR initiatives on small business performance in West Java, focusing on the interplay between CSR, entrepreneurial behavior, social capital, and empowerment.

The research questions guiding this study are:

1. How do CSR initiatives influence the entrepreneurial behavior of small businesses in West Java?
2. How does social capital mediate the relationship between CSR and small business performance?
3. How does empowerment through CSR programs contribute to the sustainability and growth of small businesses?

This study is justified by its potential contribution to academic and practical domains. Academically, it offers a comprehensive model for understanding how CSR impacts small business performance. Practically, it provides actionable insights for corporations and policymakers aiming to design effective CSR programs that foster sustainable

economic development. By focusing on PT Bio Farma's CSR initiatives, this study also highlights the role of state-owned enterprises in driving inclusive growth and community development.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Corporate Social Responsibility (Csr)

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) refers to a company's commitment to operating socially, economically, and environmentally sustainable while balancing stakeholders' interests, including shareholders, employees, customers, and the community. CSR goes beyond profit-making to include ethical, legal, and philanthropic responsibilities. In Indonesia, CSR is mandated by Law No. 40 of 2007, which requires companies to allocate funds for social and environmental initiatives. However, the amount is determined based on the company's financial capacity and fairness principles.

CSR has evolved since its introduction by Schnepf and Bowen (1954), who defined it as businesses' obligation to align their operations with societal values. Today, CSR encompasses various activities, including community development, environmental sustainability, and ethical business practices. For small businesses, CSR initiatives, such as those by PT Bio Farma, often focus on providing financial support, training, and capacity-building to enhance their performance and sustainability.

Carroll's CSR model (2016) outlines four key responsibilities: economic (profitability), legal (compliance), ethical (fairness), and philanthropic (community support). This framework is particularly relevant for small businesses, as CSR can help address challenges like limited resources and market access while fostering long-term growth and social impact. However, implementing CSR in small businesses faces challenges such as limited financial resources, lack of awareness, and organizational capacity. Despite these challenges, CSR remains a powerful tool for empowering small businesses and driving sustainable development.

2.2. Business Performance

Business performance refers to the results an organization achieves over a specific period, measured against standards such as efficiency, accountability, and the attainment of strategic goals (Zainal, 2015). According to Christianingrum *et al.* (2023), business performance reflects success in implementing programs or policies to achieve organizational objectives, vision, and mission. Suwatno and Priansa (2018) add that performance is

the outcome achieved by individuals or organizations, profit-oriented or nonprofit, within a given timeframe.

Kaplan and Norton (2001) propose that business performance can be measured through four perspectives:

1. Financial: Focuses on increasing profitability, market share, and cost efficiency.
2. Customer: Identifies customer needs and enhances satisfaction and service quality.
3. Internal Business Processes: Optimizes critical processes to deliver value to customers.
4. Learning and Growth: Builds infrastructure for innovation and human resource development.

These four perspectives help organizations achieve competitive performance and long-term sustainability.

2.3. Entrepreneurial Behavior

Entrepreneurial behavior refers to the actions and attitudes of individuals or groups in response to their environment, including natural, social, technological, or organizational contexts. It is shaped by the interaction between an individual and their surroundings, meaning that behavior varies depending on the environment (Septiana et al., 2017). Entrepreneurship involves applying creativity and innovation to solve problems, identify opportunities, and improve quality of life. Entrepreneurial behavior is characterized by recognizing business opportunities, gathering necessary resources, and taking calculated risks to ensure success.

According to Suryana (2013), entrepreneurial behavior consists of six key components: self-confidence, task and result orientation, risk-taking, leadership, originality (innovative, creative, and flexible thinking), and future orientation. These traits significantly influence business independence, and fostering these values in small business owners can enhance their self-reliance and growth (Djodjobo & Tawas, 2014). Entrepreneurial behavior is essential for driving business success and achieving long-term sustainability.

2.4. Social Capital

Social capital refers to accumulating social resources, such as networks, norms, trust, solidarity, and cooperation, that enable individuals and groups to achieve mutual benefits through collective action (Aupperle et al., 2018). It emphasizes the value of relationships built on shared values and trust within and between communities, fostering resilience and problem-solving capabilities (Suryono, 2012). Social capital is categorized into two main perspectives:

resource-based, which views it as embedded resources within social networks (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998), and network-based, which sees it as connections facilitating collaboration and value creation (Lyu & Ji, 2020).

Key components of social capital include:

1. Social Networks: Patterns of relationships that enable collective action for mutual benefit.
2. Norms: Shared rules and agreements guiding behavior.
3. Trust: Confidence in reciprocal relationships and reliability.
4. Solidarity: Willingness to support others for group benefit.
5. Cooperation: Collaborative efforts to achieve common goals (Fasya, 2013).

Social capital significantly enhances education, healthcare, political influence, disaster recovery, and economic growth. It leverages social relationships rather than financial or physical assets to generate economic or social benefits (Usman, 2018). Social capital strengthens communities and supports sustainable development by fostering trust, information sharing, and collective action.

2.5. Empowerment

Empowerment is a transformative and participatory process aimed at enhancing the capabilities of individuals and communities to address challenges and improve their quality of life (Jenkins, 2009). It is closely linked to power, enabling individuals to manage their lives and influence their environment (Park et al., 2014). Empowerment fosters creativity, self-reliance, and independence, avoiding dependency on external interventions that may undermine local autonomy (Arjaliès and Mundy, 2013).

Empowerment relies on four interdependent variables (Hena-Zapata and Peiró, 2017):

1. Sense of Community: Shared history, values, and collective experiences.
2. Competence: Ability to identify problems and agree on solutions.
3. Resources: Mobilization of human and material resources.
4. Participation: Involvement in decision-making processes.

Peng et al. (2020) identifies three key indicators of empowerment:

1. Material Change: Increased income, resource access, and improved basic needs.
2. Perceptual Change: Enhanced self-esteem, confidence, and future planning.
3. Relational Change: Greater decision-making

power, bargaining ability, and participation in community and political processes.

Empowerment is essential for sustainable development, strengthening communities, and promoting equitable growth.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research to comprehensively analyze the impact of PT Bio Farma's CSR initiatives on small business performance. The quantitative aspect uses a descriptive, explanatory survey to explore relationships between variables, while the qualitative aspect involves Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) to deepen understanding and validate findings. The research design is correlational, aiming to explore how CSR programs, social capital, and empowerment influence small business behavior and performance.

3.2. Population And Sample

The population comprises 240 small business partners of PT Bio Farma's CSR program in West Java, Indonesia. These businesses operate in various sectors, including trade, agriculture, crafts, and services. A random sampling technique was used to select 220 respondents, ensuring the sample size

meets the requirements for Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis, which recommends a sample size of 5-10 times the number of indicators (39 indicators in this study). The sample includes business owners or managers as key decision-makers.

3.3. Data Collection

Data was collected through questionnaires and FGDs. The questionnaire used a Likert scale to measure CSR partnership programs, social capital, empowerment, entrepreneurial behavior, and small business performance. FGDs were conducted with experts, CSR stakeholders, and small business representatives to gather qualitative insights and validate quantitative findings. Data collection took place from January to February 2024.

3.4. Variables And Operational Definitions

- Independent Variables: CSR partnership programs (X1), social capital (X2), and empowerment (X3).
- Dependent Variables: Entrepreneurial behavior (Z) and small business performance (Y).
- Measurement: Variables were measured using multiple indicators, such as loan accessibility, training programs, trust, income growth, and customer satisfaction.

Figure 3: Variables And Operational Definitions.

3.5. Data Analysis

The study analyzes the data using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). PLS-SEM is suitable for complex models with small sample sizes and non-normal data.

The analysis involves:

Outer Model Assessment: Evaluates the reliability and validity of the measurement model using Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE).

Composite reliability can be calculated using the formula:

$$\rho_c = \frac{(\sum \lambda_i)^2}{(\sum \lambda_i)^2 + \sum Var(\epsilon_i)}$$

Meanwhile, the formula for calculating AVE:

$$AVE = \frac{\sum \lambda_i^2}{\sum \lambda_i^2 + \sum \delta_{error}^2}$$

Where i is the component loading to the indicator to var (ei) = 1-li², if all indicators are standardized, this measure equals the Average Communalities in the block.

Inner Model Assessment: Examines the structural relationships between variables, focusing on R-

square values and path coefficients.

Hypothesis Testing: Uses t-statistics to determine the significance of relationships, with a cutoff value of 1.96 at a 0.05 significance level.

3.6 Validity And Reliability

- **Validity:** Ensured through factor loadings and cross-loadings, with items retained if their loadings exceeded 0.5.
- **Reliability:** Assessed using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability, with values above 0.6 considered reliable.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Results

1. The Effect Of CSR Partnership On Entrepreneurial Behavior

The results indicate that CSR partnerships significantly and positively affect entrepreneurial behavior, with a t-value of 5.357 (>1.96) and a path coefficient of 0.341. This means that CSR partnerships contribute 34.1% to entrepreneurial behavior, while the remaining 65.9% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study. The legal domain of CSR, particularly the provision of unrestricted business support, was the most reflective dimension. This aligns with Buendía-Martínez & Monteagudo (2020) and Luu (2020), who found that CSR significantly influences entrepreneurial behavior. The FGD participants emphasized that CSR initiatives, such as soft loans, unrestricted funding, and long-term repayment plans, positively impact entrepreneurial behavior by enhancing business knowledge and governance.

2. The Effect Of Social Capital On Entrepreneurial Behavior

Social capital also significantly and positively affects entrepreneurial behavior, with a t-value of 3.807 (>1.96) and a path coefficient of 0.231. The finding indicates that social capital contributes 23.1% to entrepreneurial behavior. The relational dimension, particularly mutual trust, was the most influential factor. This finding supports Ali & Yousuf (2020) and Mahfud et al. (2020), who highlighted the importance of social capital in fostering entrepreneurial behavior. FGD participants noted that trust-based relationships and frequent interactions between PT Bio Farma and small businesses enhance entrepreneurial behavior.

3. The Effect Of Empowerment On Entrepreneurial Behavior

Empowerment strongly and positively affects entrepreneurial behavior, with a t-value of 8.342 (>1.96) and a path coefficient of 0.406. The finding means empowerment contributes 40.6% to entrepreneurial behavior. The perceptual change dimension, particularly self-confidence, was the most reflective factor. This finding aligns with Apandi et al. (2019) and Sutawijaya and Nawangsari (2018), who emphasized the role of empowerment in enhancing entrepreneurial behavior. FGD participants highlighted that empowerment initiatives, such as creating business opportunities and fostering self-reliance, significantly improve entrepreneurial behavior.

4. The Effect Of CSR Partnership On Small Business Performance

CSR partnerships significantly and positively affect small business performance, with a t-value of 3.893 (>1.96) and a path coefficient of 0.224. This indicates that CSR partnerships contribute 22.4% to small business performance. This finding supports Basuony et al. (2014) and Wei et al. (2020), who found that CSR positively impacts business performance. However, it contradicts Yoon & Chung (2018), who reported a negative effect. FGD participants emphasized that CSR initiatives, such as soft loans and training programs, enhance small business performance by improving financial resources and business knowledge.

5. The Effect Of Social Capital On Small Business Performance

Social capital significantly and positively affect small business performance, with a t-value of 2.445 (>1.96) and a path coefficient of 0.134. This means social capital contributes 13.4% to small business performance. This finding aligns with Menike (2020) and Lyu & Ji (2020), who highlighted the role of social capital in improving business performance. However, it contradicts Meflinda & Mahyarni (2018), who found no significant effect. FGD participants noted that trust-based relationships and collaboration with various stakeholders enhance small business performance.

6. The Effect Of Empowerment On Small Business Performance

Empowerment significantly and positively affects small business performance, with a t-value of 3.971 (>1.96) and a path coefficient of 0.243. This indicates that empowerment contributes 24.3% to small business performance. This finding supports Asiedu et al. (2015) and Imamoglu et al. (2019), who

emphasized the importance of empowerment in enhancing business performance. FGD participants highlighted that empowerment initiatives, such as creating business opportunities and fostering self-reliance, significantly improve small business performance.

7. The Effect Of Entrepreneurial Behavior On Small Business Performance

Entrepreneurial behavior strongly and positively affects small business performance, with a t-value of 6.601 (>1.96) and a path coefficient of 0.400. This means entrepreneurial behavior contributes 40% to small business performance. The opportunity responsiveness dimension, particularly creating business opportunities, was the most reflective factor. This finding aligns with Amir (2017) and Pati et al. (2021), who highlighted the role of entrepreneurial behavior in improving business performance. However, it contradicts Adinoto (2010), who found no significant effect. FGD participants emphasized that entrepreneurial behavior, such as innovation and persistence, significantly enhances small business performance.

8. The Mediating Role Of Entrepreneurial Behavior

Entrepreneurial behavior partially mediates the relationship between CSR partnerships and small business performance, with a t-value of 4.696 (>1.96). Similarly, entrepreneurial behavior mediates the relationship between social capital and small business performance (t-value = 2.954) and between empowerment and small business performance (t-value = 5.174). These findings suggest that entrepreneurial behavior is crucial in translating CSR, social capital, and empowerment into improved small business performance.

4.2. Discussion

The findings highlight the critical role of CSR partnerships, social capital, and empowerment in

enhancing entrepreneurial behavior and small business performance. CSR initiatives, such as soft loans and training programs, provide small businesses with the resources and knowledge needed to improve their operations. Social capital fosters collaboration and mutual support, particularly trust-based relationships, while empowerment initiatives enhance self-reliance and innovation. Entrepreneurial behavior is a key mediator, translating these factors into improved business performance.

These results align with previous studies, such as Buendía-Martínez & Monteagudo (2020) and Apandi et al. (2022), but also reveal some contradictions, such as the findings of Yoon & Chung (2018) and Adinoto (2010). These discrepancies may be due to differences in context, sample characteristics, or measurement approaches.

The FGD insights further validate the quantitative findings, emphasizing the importance of unrestricted funding, trust-based relationships, and self-reliance initiatives in fostering entrepreneurial behavior and improving small business performance. These findings provide valuable implications for policymakers and CSR practitioners, suggesting that CSR programs should focus on building social capital, empowering small businesses, and fostering entrepreneurial behavior to achieve sustainable business growth.

5. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that CSR partnerships, social capital, and empowerment significantly influence entrepreneurial behavior and small business performance, with entrepreneurial behavior mediating. These findings underscore the importance of integrating CSR initiatives with social capital-building and empowerment programs to enhance the performance of small businesses. Future research could further explore additional mediating or moderating factors to understand the complex dynamics of small business performance.

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